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Anthaxia cylindrica ABEILLE de PERRIN, 1900 (Coleoptera: Buprestidae) – occurrence on the Rhodes Island and notes on biology

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Abstract: *A. cylindrica* is reported for the first time from the Rhodes Island. All specimens were reared from Aleppo pine (*Pinus halepensis*) – a new host plant for this species.

Key words: Coleoptera, Buprestidae, *Anthaxia cylindrica*, host plant, Greece.

INTRODUCTION

Anthaxia cylindrica ABEILLE de Perrin, 1900 is a species known from the eastern Mediterranean basin. The species has so far been recorded from Cyprus, Lebanon, Syria and Turkey (KUBÁŇ 2016). Features that differentiate *A. cylindrica* from other, related taxa were presented i.a. by ABEILLE de PERRIN (1900), MAGNANI (1993), and OBENBERGER (1938).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

– Greece, Rhodes Island, Kiotari (36.0643 N, 27.9959 E): 25 II 2022-15 VIII 2022, 36 exx., reared from thin Aleppo Pine (*Pinus halepensis* MILL.) branches with a diameter of 12-22 mm, collected on 24 IX 2021, leg. et cult. M. Miłkowski (Fig. 1A, B). The branches came from small, shrubby pines growing adjacent to the seashore. Collected specimens of *A. cylindrica* are in the author's collections, as well as the collections of R. Królik, J. Ługowoj, J. Mendzikowski.

This is the first information about *A. cylindrica* from the Rhodes Island. The biotope and the larval feeding pattern in pine branches are shown in Fig. 2A, B. A larval feeding pattern generally does not differ from that of known *Anthaxia* species that develop in the wood of coniferous trees.

We believe that this species is associated with pine trees. ULAY & TEZCAN (1998) also reported other host plants: *Cistus* sp., *Quercus* sp., and *Pyrus elaeagnifolia*. However, this information has not been confirmed, and seems unreliable. The species *A. laticeps navratili* (BÍLÝ 1984), described from Crete, was compared by us to *A. cylindrica*. Based on the

comparison, we believe that this is probably the same species, but additional research is required to confirm this. It is noteworthy that both species were reared from the same host plant, the Aleppo pine (*P. halepensis*), which may further support such opinion.

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Fig. 1. Male (A) and female (B) *Anthaxia cylindrica* (scale bar 1mm).

Fig. 2. The biotope (A) and the larval *Anthaxia cylindrica* feeding pattern in Aleppo Pine *Pinus halepensis* branches (B).

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